

Testing of Heat Operated Adsorption Refrigeration System for Space Cooling

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Abstract

Now a day due to development of economy and research in science the standard of living increases worldwide and hence energy consumption in the houses, building, corporate offices is increase worldwide. In case of air conditioning the HVAC system is developed and electrically driven vapor compression air conditioning unit specially in hot weather. Electrically driven VCR consumes very high grade energy and it is also hazardous to our environment. On other hand thermally driven adsorption refrigeration and systems got considerable attention now a day not due to its manufacturing simplicity, but also having environment friendly adsorbent /refrigerant pairs. This paper work is aim for testing a prototype of vapour adsorption refrigeration system using aqua ammonia and 1KW capacity has been tested in the laboratory of vapour adsorption. In present work the heating time required to achieve the cooling effect is around 10 minutes.

Keywords: Adsorption system, Ammonia-Activated carbon, Heat source, Renewable energy.

1. Introduction

In heat operated adsorption refrigeration system heat source is used to compress refrigerant rather than electric compressor. In adsorption refrigeration system important parts are vessel

which contains adsorbant-refrigerant pair called generator and evaporator condenser along with expansion valve is used to complete adsorption refrigeration system. Adsorption refrigeration system is similar as absorption refrigeration system in which difference of a solid adsorbing material instead of liquid absorbing material. Adsorption refrigeration technology operates in low grade energy that is heat. In this refrigeration system the refrigerants used have zero ozone layer depletion potential and very low global warming potential. Adsorption system is driven by thermal energy, any kind of acceptable heat energy, which can be obtained from combustion of fuel which is a waste heat from engine exhaust. In adsorption refrigeration system the compressor of a conventional vapor compression refrigeration system is replaced by an adsorption compressor, which gives thermal compression powered by suitable heat source. In an adsorption system moving parts are very less like valves are required. As there is no mechanical compressor it requires no lubrication, it is simple in operation and very less maintenance is required. Adsorption refers to the binding of molecules (sorbate) to the surface of a material (sorbent) without any change.

1.1 Thermodynamic Cycle of adsorption refrigeration

Schematic of Thermodynamic Cycle of adsorption refrigeration

1. Process1-2(Isosteric desorption)

The cool adsorber is heated and desorbs refrigerant vapour isothermally (i.e. at constant total mass in the adsorber), to state 2 slightly above P_{cond} .

2. Process2-3(Isobaric desorption)

Isobaric heating desorbs more refrigerant, forcing it into the condenser until state 3 attained, where the adsorber is nearly devoid of refrigerant.

3 Process3-4(Isosteric adsorption)

The hot adsorber is then cooled isothermally (at constant total mass), causing adsorption and depressurization, until the pressure drops below P_{evap} (state4), opening another check valve to allow vapour to enter the adsorber from the evaporator.

3. Process4-1(Isobaric adsorption)

Isobaric cooling to state1 the refrigerant saturates the adsorbent and thus completing the cycle.

1.2 Working pair

The working pair is the crucial part of adsorption refrigeration system. The basic properties which are required for adsorption refrigeration are large adsorption capacity, large change in adsorption capacity with change in temperature and compatibility with refrigerant and low adsorption heat. The basic properties a refrigerant should possess are same as that required in a vapour compression system.

2. Literature review

Habib et al. [5] have analyzed the performance of combined ADRS (with 70°C energy source) in which a heat exchanger is used not only as an evaporator, but also as a condenser at the same time. By Using R134a and activated carbon

adsorbent for high cycle and activated carbon adsorbent R507a refrigerant for low cycle, they reached the result of 85 kW cooling capacity with 10⁰C chilled water outlet temperature, and 0.069 coefficient of performance.

Tamainot-Telto et al. [6] Investigated Carbon ammonia pairs for adsorption refrigeration applications. The simulation results of 26 various activated carbon ammonia pairs for three cycles (single bed, two-bed and infinite number of beds). The carbon adsorbents investigated were mainly coconut shell and coal based types in multiple forms: monolithic, granular, compacted granular, fiber, compacted fiber, cloth, compacted cloth and powder and the driving temperature varied from 80⁰C to 200⁰C.

H. Tiwari et al. [8] presented design development and experimentation of an adsorption refrigeration system powered by exhaust heat with only two control valves. The cooling capacity for a truck cabin is estimated as 1 TR a scale of 3.5:1 is decided and a prototype of 1 kW has been designed and developed and tested in laboratory. A cooling effect of 1 to 1.2 kW has been obtained. The COP of the system is in the range of 0.4 to 0.45. The dimensions of the system are compact. It can be easily accommodated on a Transport Truck. The total weight of the system for a cooling capacity of 1 kW is 30 kg. The heating time required to achieve the cooling effect is around 10 minute.

W.S. Chang et al. [9] designed and tested an adsorption cooling system with silica gel as the adsorbent and water as the adsorbate. This was experimentally studied to reduce the manufacturing costs and simplify the construction of the adsorption cooling system. a vacuum tank was designed to contain the adsorption bed and evaporator/condenser. Flat-tube type heat exchangers were used for adsorption beds in order to increase the heat transfer area and improve the heat transferability between the adsorbent and heat exchanger fins. Under the standard test t

conditions of 80°C hot water, 30°C cooling water, and 14°C chilled water in let temperatures, a cooling power of 4.3 kW and a coefficient of performance (COP) for cooling of 0.45 was achieved. It provided a specific cooling power (SCP) of about 176 W/ (kg adsorbent). With lower hot water flow rates, a higher COP of 0.53 was achieved.

Meng et al. [14] studied the energy saving mechanism of an adsorption and vapour compression hybrid refrigeration cycle with a working pair of R134a and DMF. Based on their two newly proposed criteria, comparing with the compression refrigeration cycle, this hybrid refrigeration cycle could save 16.1 to 67.1% of electricity under generating temperatures of 60°C to 90°C.

2.2 Literature gap

After studying literature review we come to know that two bed adsorption systems are less developed. In existing adsorption system there is a scope on study of initial pressure and heating time cycle. To achieve maximum COP, we can focus on these two parameter.

3. Testing Procedure

1. Before testing of the project, it is verified that system is leak proof by performing leakage test.
2. The Vacuum is then produced by using Vacuum pump.
3. The system is charged with ammonia, after charging the initial pressure in the system was 3 to 5 bar.
4. Check whether the water connections are proper or not. Start the tap water for cooling of two condenser units and one absorber generator unit.

5. The fuel consumption is measure by taking the weight of the kerosene filled blower stove before heating and after heating.
6. Start the blower stove for heating of charged Absorber-Generator unit. Heat the Absorber-Generator unit for 10 minutes. The pressure after heating should be close to 15 bars.
7. Open the Expansion Valve gradually, the pressurized liquid ammonia from condenser, expands up to evaporator pressure and produces refrigerating effect in Evaporator coil.
8. The vapour ammonia adsorbed by Absorber-Generator unit which is in cooling mode.
9. Now heating and cooling cycles are altered for second trial and procedure is repeated.

4 Observation Table

Sr.No	Parameter	Trial 1		Trial 2		Trial 3		Trial 4		Trial 5		Trial 6		Trial 7	
		I	F	I	F	I	F	I	F	I	F	I	F	I	F
1	T_1	21	20	21	20	20	20	21	21	20	20	22	20	22	22
2	T_2	21	20	19	21	22	19	21	21	20	21	23	21	24	21
3	T_3	28	7	27	5	29	7	28	7	31	9	28	7	28	6
4	T_4	22	9	23	7	23	9	25	10	23	10	23	9	23	8
5	T_5	28	15	28	14	30	16	29	15	28	14	28	16	27	17
6	P	4	11.3	3	10.6	4	11	2	9.9	4	12	4	12	4	12

Sr. no	Heating Time (s)	COP
Trial 1	600	0.33
Trial 2	630	0.22
Trial 3	660	0.22
Trial 4	690	0.31
Trial 5	720	0.40
Trial 6	750	0.33
Trial 7	780	0.22

5. Results

5 CONCLUSION

1. 111.37 kJ to 278.44 kJ refrigerating effect generated from system with a COP of 0.33 for the adsorption system.

2. As the heating time increases the COP increases up to 0.4.

6 FUTURE SCOPE

1. The proposed system can operate with multiple heat sources like solar energy or other waste heat sources. Such systems can be developed and tested.
2. Research can be done with other working pairs of adsorbent and refrigerant like R- 134a and activated carbon, methanol and activated carbon etc. and performances can be compared.
3. A further research can be done in vapour adsorption refrigeration system for a small capacity as it is not available for small sizes.

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